

RECONFIGURABLE MODULAR BAR STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Structural modularity and reconfiguration allow for enhanced flexibility and adaptability to changing functional, environmental or loading conditions, contributing thus to a sustainable built up environment. The current paper refers to a temporary spatial structure of planar modular bar linkages positioned in parallel and interconnected. The linkages consist of hinge-connected beams and a secondary system of joints and continuous cables with adjustable length. Identical and synchronous reconfiguration of the planar systems provide respective shapes of the spatial structure. In achieving the transformations, the effective 4-bar approach is implemented via cable-driven actuation, necessitating only two linear actuators on the planar systems supports. Following a brief description of the reconfiguration approach and related motion planning principles, a presentation of the fabrication and assembly of a small-scale prototype model and its experimental testing leads to a discussion on related mechanical design and reconfiguration approach issues. By extent, a Finite-Element Analysis of the spatial structure conducted for a specific transformation sequence followed from an initial to a target configuration provides further insight in the system's nonlinear load-bearing behavior.

Keywords: Reconfigurable Structures, Motion Planning and Control, Effective 4-Bar Method, Cable-driven Actuation, Finite-Element Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Building structures that are able to respond to different physical environments, functions and configurations together with advances in digital and numerical computing technology open up new research directions for an investigation of their morphology and behavior. Structural modularity allows a high degree of flexibility to be achieved from the basic element, to the planar, up to the spatial structure with regard to the morphological outcome [1]. In describing the search for lighter and more efficient structures and technologies, while achieving more with less resources, the term 'ephemeralization', implying also temporariness was proposed [2]. Structural reconfiguration in real time allows for further adaptability to changing functional, loading or environmental conditions,

contributing thus to a sustainable built up environment [3]. In this framework, the term 'reconfigurable' refers specifically to the ability of the system to control its movement with computational assistance and according to control algorithms, an area that has been only recently introduced and explored in architecture and the construction industry.

From a technical perspective, Buckminster Fuller, worked intensively for over fifty years on self-supporting modular constructions and geodesic domes, based on principles of prefabrication and standardization, industrial production and erection process [2]. The same is true of Konrad Wachsmann [4]. The USAF Hangar Project is characteristic for the development of a modular syntax of design enabling folding, partitioning and easy

transportation of the structural components, a universal system joint and industrial production of the components.

The idea of modularity can be found among other works on ‘hierarchical modular structures’ [5], on modular robots with local control abilities leading to multiple systems’ configurations [6], or where the assembly – disassembly of modules controls the entire system configuration [7]. Examples such as the ‘Polybot’ [8], the ‘Macrobot’ [9] and the ‘HyperMorphology’ [10] are based on similar principles evolving modular design logic and reconfigurable mechanisms, in order to achieve adaptation and hence changeability of their morphology, as well as automation of their functions. Thus, modularity and structural control based on robotic principles may formulate main pillars, where an informed design strategy for the system’s comprehensive development can be achieved.

Concurrently, reconfigurable structures of different typologies and mechanisms have been developed in recent years for architectural and engineering applications, primarily in terms of deployable structures, in relation to requirements of temporary environments [11]. In this frame, tensegrity and scissor-like systems have been proposed to provide transformability.

In particular, tensegrity structures (i.e. self-stressed systems composed of tension and compression members), are characterized by their physical properties in providing a holistic and integrated composition of embedded active control. Also, the specific typology comprises autonomous and self-supported systems, while effectively transferring the loading [12]. In principle, the transformation of ‘static tensegrities’ in kinetic systems is based on the replacement of compression members with linear pneumatic actuators, or the implementation of tension members with variable length [13-15].

Although structures with embedded actuators in place of primary joints or members are usually designed to use a small number of components to achieve a maximum number of shape adjustments, implementation requires designers to deal with an increase of the structure’s weight (depending on the number and characteristics of the actuators used), complex mechanisms and energy-inefficient operation. Related improvements refer to the interconnection of the compression members and the

reduction of actuators through clustering of continuous cables (e.g. strut-routed actuation) and their actuation at the supports of the structure [16].

Other common types of deployable structures include planar and spatial scissor-hinge elements. These have the ability to expand in both, horizontal and vertical direction [17-19]. While such structural elements need additional stabilizing members like cables or other locking devices, self-stable structures can be achieved with the application of special geometrical configurations through additional inner scissor-like elements. A considerable advancement in the design of such systems was made with the development of the simple angulated element [20, 21]. However, scissor-like elements do not provide extensive flexibility, since their motion is limited between an open and closed state. In this respect, a novel planar and spatial scissor-hinge mechanism is proposed in [22, 23].

As in the aforementioned cases, the development of reconfigurable structures constitutes a multidisciplinary approach, which embraces from early stages, architecture, structural and control engineering aspects. Related concepts from kinematics, dynamics and control of robotic systems become relevant. Along these lines, the current paper refers to the development of a reconfigurable temporary structure of repeatable identical modules, that integrates the structural and physical control mechanism components and achieves conceptual simplicity on the structural typology, flexibility with regard to the transformability of the system and minimum number of actuators placed on the supports, instead of on the main structure body, for reduced energy consumption during reconfigurations. In the following sections, the reconfiguration approach proposed for planar linkage systems will be presented, together with the related constraints of the mechanical system design and the kinematic characteristics of the system. The fabrication of the modular components of a 9-bar linkage planar system in scale 1:5 for experimental prototype testing conducted by the authors will be described in Section 4. Finally, the load-bearing behavior of the spatial structure will be numerically investigated based on nonlinear Finite-Element Analysis (FEA) for a specific sequence pattern involving six reconfiguration steps, from an initial to a target configuration. The Conclusions section discusses the main features of the modular reconfigurable system with regard to its composition, static and kinetic behavior.

2. RECONFIGURATION APPROACH

The reconfiguration approach proposed for achieving versatility in applications applies to planar linkage systems of modular components arranged in parallel to form the spatial structure. A reconfiguration of the building would involve the coordinated motion of each individual n -bar linkage, composed of $(n-1)$ serially connected members with rotational joints between them and linked to the ground through pivot joints on either side. Each joint of the mechanism could then be installed with a brake mechanism, whose operation is linked to the control system. A planar n -bar linkage has $(n-3)$ degrees-of-freedom (DOF) and motion control requires equal number of motion actuators. Reconfigurations of the individual linkages accordingly would adjust the overall shape of the building. Nevertheless, this means that multiple actuators would need to be attached to the main structure and increase respectively the structure's self-weight and the energy consumption during reconfigurations. In order to avoid this and at the same time, achieve flexibility and controllability in the structure's kinematics, a multistep procedure has been proposed [24, 25]. Each step involves the selective locking of $(n-4)$ joints of the primary members to define a corresponding 'effective 4-bar' mechanism (E4B), which is a 1-DOF system. The ground itself provides one member of each component linkage. Through actuation, one angle is adjusted to the desired value and the remaining are locked until the overall reconfiguration is completed. During the next step a different set of brakes is applied and the procedure is repeated until all the joint angles are adjusted to their target value. The final E4B realization serves to simultaneously adjust the position of the last remaining four joints. Therefore, a complete reconfiguration between an initial and a final posture of each n -bar linkage requires a total of $(n-3)$ intermediate steps. Throughout the structure reconfigurations only slow motions are involved and inertial effects are negligible.

Following the E4B approach, a direct actuation would involve only one actuated joint at the base employing either a rotational or a linear actuator [26]. In Fig. 1a) activated brakes are represented with a crossed circle and released brakes are represented with a dotted circle. A group of neighboring links with locked joints between them constitutes an 'effective link'. A more elaborate actuation method presented here is associated to a system of cables and

two corresponding linear actuators that handle the reconfiguration (Fig. 1b) [25]. The cables are associated with a system of pulleys and struts installed at each individual joint. A passive linkage is used for centering the struts with respect to the corresponding joint. The cables are thus applied as actuation means in the kinetic system and act together with the struts as secondary strengthening components of the static system once a reconfiguration step has been completed. During joint adjustments depending on the required direction of motion, the actuation task is appropriately assigned by the controller to one of the two cable systems. The cable needs to be either pulled or released depending on the tendency of the structure to move under the effect of gravity. Following this method, the control action is distributed simultaneously at two joints of the E4B mechanism.

Figure 1: The effective 4-bar concept for the 9-bar system (\otimes : locked joint, \odot : unlocked joint, Δ : pivoted-to-the-ground joint) applied at a transformation step between the initial and target positions of the systems; a) n -bar linkage with effective 4-bar; b) system configuration and cable-driven actuation

3. MOTION PLANNING

A reconfiguration between an initial and a final position of an n -bar linkage system can be performed through alternative control sequences. Motion planning of the E4B approach considers certain constraints of the mechanical system design and the kinematic characteristics of the system. In all cases, both joints pivoted to the ground always remain unlocked and no link can move below the horizontal ground level. Furthermore, each intermediate reconfiguration step is concluded with the adjustment of one joint angle, which remains locked from then on. Specifically, in the cable-driven actuation method, two consecutively unlocked joints, or an even number of locked joints between the two unlocked ones is required, so that the cable actions (generated torques at the joints) do not

compete with each other as a consequence of the zig-zag winding of the cables between the struts. Once a reconfiguration step has been completed and the structure joints are locked, the opposing action generated simultaneously by the two cables, enables respective stiffness adjustment [27, 28]. This is a topic of current research in robotics [29, 30], but will not be pursued further in this paper. Finally, an upper limit of 175° of any unlocked cable joint angle should avoid infeasible sequences.

4. EXPERIMENTAL TESTING

The E4B reconfiguration method has been implemented on a 9-bar computer-controlled setup in scale 1:5 that was developed for this purpose (Fig. 25). The experimental implementation of the structural prototype and the investigation of the cable-driven actuation method for a specific reconfiguration sequence provided insight to the composition of the structure and its modular components, as well as to the reconfiguration method and its application specifics [31].

Figure 2: Experimental setup of a planar 9-bar linkage configured for the implementation of the cable-driven actuation method.

The model includes all modular structural components together with the sensors and actuators required for control (Fig. 3). The structural model is composed of links with 350 mm length, struts of 300 mm length and 8 mm diameter, and diagonal members of 74 mm length. Plexiglas was used for the beams and the diagonal alignment members, stainless-steel for the struts, polylactic acid (PLA) for the secondary components and steel for the joint shafts. The planar 9-bar linkage is mounted to move on the vertical plane and the beams are hinge-connected through rotational joints. The two ends of the linkage are pinned to a ground-fixed base. The structural members are also hinge-connected to the slider that moves along the length of the struts using the two auxiliary diagonal members. Appropriate

bearings were installed to reduce friction and backlash in the motion system.

a)

b)

Figure 3: a) Off-the-shelf structural components; b) control components of the 9-bar system

The joint assembly and its details are shown in Fig. 4. In the experimental setup, the brake system of the joints (except the base joints) includes a cylindrical steel block with a symmetric array of holes on its curved surface for locking the joint when two stopper pins are inserted from both sides. In the experimental testing of the structure, locking the joint was thus limited to a set of fixed, discrete positions, corresponding to 120° , 144° , and 168° internal joint angles. This discretization of the joint rotations introduced an extra motion planning constraint. The spring-loaded pins of the brake system maintain the joint at a locked position and they are released upon

Figure 4: Realization of joint details (intermediate joint and base joint) of the 9-bar system based on the cable-driven actuation method

activating their electromagnets (solenoids). This ensures a fail-safe operation of the brakes system. On each joint the pair of electromagnets is wired in parallel to lock/release the joint simultaneously with the same control signal.

The control system is responsible for implementing the stepwise reconfigurations. For each reconfiguration step the control system issues commands to selectively release some of the brakes. Then, the linear motion actuators perform the actual reconfiguration, while the controller receives feedback information from the sensors regarding the current position of the joints. Actuation of the system is based on electric linear actuators (12V DC, 150 cm travel). The two linear actuators have been employed to tension the two corresponding cables and perform a stepwise reconfiguration. The stainless-steel cables pass through the pulleys that are attached on the struts. The required angular position measurements are provided by potentiometer-type sensors, which provide continuous, absolute position measurements without requiring an initialization (homing) procedure. The position sensors have been integrated to each joint assembly except of the two at the base. The system is computer controlled through a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that presents the user with the current joint positions and includes buttons for controlling the operation of the linear actuators and the brakes.

The experimental testing of the 9-bar linkage served primarily the verification of the modular component assembly, connectivity issues, the system's kinematics and actuation. Several reconfiguration sequences have been successfully implemented, and the effectiveness of the E4B approach was verified. At the same time some practical limitations of the method became clear. At a mechanical design level, certain control difficulties may arise from the friction inherent in the joints' locking mechanism, since the self-weight of the structure often opposes the release of the locked joints. Furthermore, pretension in the cables is necessary, in order to ensure smooth transition between consecutive reconfiguration steps and to prevent slack of the members. Added to that, the inherent cable elasticity and friction on the cable routing system of pulleys play a significant role in the effective distribution of the cable force to the unlocked joints of the linkage.

5. STATIC ANALYSIS

The nonlinear FEA refers to the load-bearing and dynamic behavior of the 3-dimensional arch-like

building structure of the 9-bar linkages. The case assessment for a specific sequence pattern involving six different reconfiguration steps, from an initial to a target configuration, has been simulated with the Finite-Element Analysis software program SAP2000. The aim of the investigation was to study the 3-dimensional structure behavior in its different reconfiguration steps under static vertical and horizontal loading. The load-cases considered in the analysis include the self-weight of the structure, a uniformly distributed surface vertical load of 2.5 kN/m² and a wind load of 1 kN/m². The analysis conducted considered no geometric or loading imperfections, nor any initial deformation of the system in each reconfiguration step.

The structure is composed of ten parallel arch-like configurations of a 9-bar linkage, positioned at a distance of 2 m in the longitudinal axis. The linkages are horizontally interconnected at the joints through compression members and diagonal cables for the diaphragm constraint at the roof plane (Fig. 5). The overall shape of the spatial structure is obtained from identical and synchronous reconfigurations of the individual planar systems. The membrane cover is assumed to have exclusive elastic deformations and minimal stress interactions that would result due to differentiated reconfigurations or relative

Figure 5: Spatial structure composed of ten 9-bar linkages arranged in parallel: a) Initial position; b) target position

deformations between any adjacent primary planar linkages. Two alternative designs for the envelope structure were presented at conceptual architectural level in [32].

The 9-bar linkage consists of hinge connected beam members and a secondary system of struts and continuous cables with variable length. The struts comprise continuous members with overall length of 1.5 m, symmetrically positioned with respect to the joint. The continuous cables with variable length pass through pulleys at the upper and lower strut points. The members' sections are as follows: beams, 2 x UPN 120/100 mm, struts, round hollow section 60/10 mm, horizontal compression members, round hollow section 80/10 mm, and cables, \varnothing 20 mm. The beams have 1.75 m length each and the continuous cables, approximately 20 m length. Aluminum of 69.6 GPa elastic modulus and 241.3 MPa yield strength is assigned for the beam members, the struts and the horizontal members of the structure. The cables are assigned to steel S450 of 24.82 GPa elastic modulus. In principle, the bi-linear model without hardening has been assumed for the material modelling.

The structural system with span of 5.00 m, has an initial configuration of 5.35 m height, and a target configuration of 4.20 m height, following a quasi-vertical and horizontal ellipsoid shape, respectively. The initial and target configuration are given by $\theta_i = [97,168,155,131,157,131,155,168,97]^T$ and $\theta_f = [130,128,133,158,163,158,133,128,130]^T$ degrees of the internal n -bar angles, respectively. The joints of the 9-bar linkages are assumed to be controlled through electromagnetic brakes, for having flexibility in the joint angle adjustment during each reconfiguration step. In the structural analysis, the modelling of the joints is based on the direct stiffness method, i.e. the system is modelled as a set of idealized elements interconnected at the nodes, and the analysis makes use of the members' stiffness relations for computing the members' forces and displacements. Fig. 6 shows the scheduling table for a specific control sequence applied to realize the required shape adjustment. The corresponding reconfiguration steps of the system motion sequence are shown in Fig. 7.

J ₁	J ₂	J ₃	J ₄	J ₅	J ₆	J ₇	J ₈	J ₉
△	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊙	△
△	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊙	⊗	△
△	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	△
△	⊗	⊙	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	△
△	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	△
△	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	△

Figure 6: Scheduling table for a control sequence adopted to realize the required shape adjustment (⊗: locked joint, ⊙: unlocked joint, △: pivoted-to-the-ground joint, shaded symbols represent the currently adjusted joints)

The cables of the planar system have been modelled as cable elements with undeformed length. They are assigned with a pretension value of 2 kN. The supports of the system are considered as pinned connections together with the remaining unlocked joints in each reconfiguration step. The analysis results for the structure refer to the respective maximum values obtained from either case, of having two unlocked internal joints by the time a reconfiguration step has been completed, and following this, when all internal joints are locked at the same respective position.

Seven different configurations of the spatial structure have been evaluated including the initial one, with regard to their static behavior. Fig. 8 illustrates the deformations of the structure in all reconfiguration steps, under vertical load, wind load and the two load-combination, while the wire curve represents the undeformed configuration at the respective posture. Figs 9, 10 illustrate the maximum deformations for the overall structure in x- and z-axis with unlocked (j-) and locked (j+) system joints, under self-weight (q), vertical (Q), wind load (W) and their combination (Q+W). In these cases, the respective highest values in the diagrams refer to the maximum values obtained once each reconfiguration step has been completed, before locking of the joints of the system. Figs 11-14 present the maximum internal forces in the members, i.e. beam axial force

Figure 7: Motion sequence of 9-bar linkage system

N_b , shear force Q_b , moment M_b , and axial cable force N_c with unlocked (j-) and locked (j+) system joints. In the case of the maximum axial cable force again, the highest maximum values derive from the configurations at the respective steps, with unlocked joints of the systems.

Figure 8: Maximum structure deformations of configurations' deformations

The configuration in step 2 with its respective joints unlocked, registered the highest maximum horizontal deformation of 5 cm under the self-weight of the structure. By a vertical load increase up to the assigned value of 5 kN/m, the system configurations in step 2 and 3 with unlocked joints have increased maximum horizontal deformations of 37 and 32 cm, respectively (Fig. 9). With locked system joints, a highest maximum horizontal deformation of 2 and 30 cm is registered in steps 2-4 and in step 2, under the self-weight and vertical load, respectively. The initial configuration of the system, with a quasi-vertical ellipsoid shape in span direction, has 0.09 and 2 cm maximum horizontal deformation under the self-weight and vertical load, respectively.

Figure 9: Maximum structure deformations in x-axis

The configurations in steps 1 and 2 with the respective joints unlocked, have highest maximum vertical deformations of 4 cm, under the self-weight. Furthermore, the configurations in steps 2 and 6 with the respective joints unlocked, registered the highest maximum vertical deformations of 37 and 32 cm, under vertical load and the combination of vertical and horizontal load respectively (Fig. 10). A noticeably reduced system deformation of 0.1, 2, 4 and 5 cm, is registered in the initial configuration, under the self-weight, vertical, horizontal and their combination, respectively. With locked system joints, a highest maximum vertical deformation of 2 and 28 cm is registered in steps 2 and 3 under self-weight and in step 2 under vertical load.

The structural system with highest flexibility, has a fundamental period T_1 of 0.68s in reconfiguration step 1. The initial configuration has a fundamental period of 0.39 s. The respective configuration in step 5 registered the lowest maximum value, reduced by 56.35 %. With regard to the second period of the system, T_2 , the initial and final configuration registered the highest values of 0.15 and 0.14 s with unlocked system joints, and 0.11 s, with locked joints, respectively.

Figure 10: Maximum structure deformations in z-axis

The system configuration in step 2 registered the highest maximum axial beam force of 7.47 kN with its respective joints unlocked, and 15.5 kN with locked joints, under the self-weight. The respective configurations with unlocked system joints, with highest maximum values of axial beam force under vertical load and combination of vertical and horizontal load, were registered in step 5 with values of 162.63 and 142.48, respectively. In the case that all system joints are locked, a respective highest maximum axial beam force of 154.92 and 134.55, is registered in the same step, under the same loads. A respective lowest maximum value of 6.07, 35.18, 12.41 and 47.57 kN is registered in the initial configuration, under the self-weight, vertical, horizontal load and their combination, respectively (Fig. 11).

The highest maximum shear beam force of 2.16 and 33.76 kN, with unlocked joints, under self-weight and vertical load is registered in both cases, in configuration step 6. With locked joints of the system, the highest maximum shear beam force of 1.55 and 30.50 kN is registered again in both cases,

in step 5. The lowest maximum value of 0.30 and 8.42 kN is registered in the initial configuration, (Fig. 12).

Figure 11: Maximum axial structure beam forces

Figure 12: Maximum shear structure beam forces

The highest and lowest maximum torque of the beams of 3.28, 2.56 and 0.56 kNm, under the self-weight is registered in configuration step 2 with unlocked system joints, in step 3 with locked joints and in the initial configuration, respectively. The respective highest and lowest maximum values under vertical load, of 43.40, 37.97 and 9.21 kNm are registered in configuration step 3 with unlocked system joints, in step 4 with locked joints and in the initial configuration, respectively. The respective maximum reduction in the latter configuration amounts to 78.78 % (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Maximum torques in structure joints

The configuration in step 6 registered the highest maximum axial cable force of 3.17 kN under the self-weight of the structure. Furthermore, in steps 5 and 6 the values of 38.78 and 38.61, and 47.22 and 38.78 kN, are registered under vertical load and the combination of vertical and horizontal load, respectively. The initial configuration registered a minimum axial cable force of 2.03, 4.52, 7.06 and 8.41 kN, under the self-weight, vertical, horizontal load and their combination (Fig. 14).

The system configuration in step 1 with unlocked joints registered the highest maximum horizontal and vertical deformations of 20 and 14 cm respectively under wind load, while the initial configuration deformations amount to 12 and 4 cm, respectively. The respective highest deformation values of the system with locked joints amount to 12 and 9 cm. Under wind load, the system with unlocked joints develops highest maximum values of 42.41 kN, 13.71 kN, 13.79 kNm and 18.39 kN, with locked joints, 23.33 kN, 15.91 kN, 19.06 kNm and 10.00 kN, of axial beam force, shear beam force, torque and axial cable force. The highest maximum axial beam and cable force are registered in step 1. The highest maximum shear beam force and torque are registered in step 5. The configuration in step 2 registered the lowest maximum shear and torque value of 2.40 kN and 8.37 kNm, respectively.

Figure 14: Maximum axial structure cable forces

6. CONCLUSIONS

Traditional buildings have been fixed-shape structures. A new generation of reconfigurable buildings will provide opportunities for improved

performance in various aspects including energy efficiency, occupants comfort, space utilization, reduced structural loading from wind, and aesthetics. This perspective has triggered research and development in reconfigurable/adaptive architecture. At the same time enabling technologies including structural engineering, new materials, control systems, sensors and actuators provide modern, affordable and efficient solutions. Research interest has been both from an architectural and engineering perspective to resolve the respective aspects. Unavoidably, the aforementioned benefits are associated with increased complexity, initial costs, and extra operational and maintenance costs when compared to fixed-shape structures. Particular demands may also be imposed on flexible membranes when used to form a variable building envelope. Safety and reliability are also key issues to be resolved. Clearly, engineering tradeoffs are involved, so that reconfigurable structures constitute a feasible and attractive option in architectural design.

In this frame, the current paper presented a modular spatial structure that is composed of parallel positioned bar linkage systems. The structure may serve temporary functional purposes and be adaptable to changing external environment or loading conditions. Based on the assumption that the envelope membrane cover has adequate elasticity to follow the reconfigurations of the structure with no significant stress interaction, identical and synchronous reconfigurations of the individual planar linkages provide corresponding differentiated overall shapes of the spatial structure. The planar linkages consist of modular components, i.e. hinge connected beams and a secondary system of struts and continuous cables with variable length that primarily serve as actuation means for the system reconfigurations. The modularity of the structure enables rapid assembly, deployability, transformability and reusability of the components. It also enables variability of the geometrical characteristics of the members in obtaining further system shapes with differentiated span and height, as well as easy expandability in the longitudinal direction through respective addition of planar linkages. A disadvantage in this regard is the inherent axis hierarchy followed by the spatial system that conforms to a grid of orthogonal axes yielding parallel configurations.

At kinematics level, the E4B approach has been implemented in preserving minimum structural self-

weight and energy consumption during reconfigurations, whereas any target configuration of the system is achieved over stepwise unlocking and adjustment of the individual system joint angles through respective tensioning or releasing of the cables. The reconfiguration approach is realized with only two linear actuators at the supports of the structure, and without these being attached to the main structure body. Consequently, no actuators need to be moved about during the reconfigurations of the system, yielding better energy efficiency.

A prototype model of the system has been fabricated in scale 1:5, assembled and experimentally tested to verify aspects of the mechanical design, with regard to the components and their connections, the control mechanism and reconfiguration approach. The connections of the components and the brake system of the control mechanism have proven to be critical. In particular, the joints locking mechanism should be designed to operate with minimum friction, as well as the cable elasticity and friction on the routing system of the pulleys should be kept to a minimum for an effective implementation.

FEA of the spatial structure referred to its nonlinear load bearing behavior at the intermediate reconfiguration steps of a specific sequence followed for the transformation of the system from an initial to a target configuration. Based on the results obtained, the members are stressed within their elastic region. Under the self-weight of the structure, the resulting deformations are limited. The highest respective value amounts 5 cm, obtained in reconfiguration step 2 with unlocked system joints. Furthermore, the analysis showed that excessive deformations may develop with vertical load increase. A highest respective value of 37 cm was registered in the same step with unlocked system joints, under a vertical load of 5 kN/m. At this point it is noted that the experimental study of the prototype has by no means validated the Finite-Element model. The FEA results enable at first place, a global understanding of the problematic, but the exact value of the deformations has not been experimentally proven. In all cases it is essential that the structural members consist of lightweight material, in order to keep the self-weight of the structure as low as possible. At the same time, this comes at cost to the resulting deformations of the system, necessitating a stiffness increase of the primary members' sections used. A respective balance between lightweight, high stiffness and strengthening measures of the members needs to be

found, while also considering the temporary character of the reconfigurable structure. In all cases the criteria of joint torques and system deformations are decisive in selecting an appropriate sequence for reconfiguration of the system from an initial to a target position. In this respect, further research is planned for the development of automated selection processes of optimized sequences among feasible ones, i.e. upon considering the motion and actuation constraints based on the aforementioned criteria.

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